

**PHOTOVOLTAIC POWER WITHOUT BATTERIES FOR CONTINUOUS
CATHODIC PROTECTION AND AN ALTERNATE
PHOTOVOLTAIC/ULTRACAPACITOR COMBINED POWER SOURCE**

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ABSTRACT - The Coastal Systems Station (COASTSYSTA) designed, installed, and started up on 20 January 1990, a state-of-the-art stand-alone photovoltaic powered impressed current cathodic protection system (PVCPSYS) not requiring any backup power for steel and iron submerged structures. The PVCPSYS, installed on a 775-foot steel sheet piling of a Navy dock bulkhead, provides complete, continuous corrosion protection. The PVCPSYS has been in operation for more than five years, has not required any repair or maintenance, and is environmentally clean. Initial cost savings of the PVCPSYS versus conventional cathodic protection system was \$46,000. A second PVCPSYS was installed on another 800-foot bulkhead on 21 May 1993. It is also providing complete corrosion protection without backup power. Performance is well documented. Other potential applications are moth-balled ships, locks, dams, bridges, pipelines, and similar structures. These systems are considered a major advance by Sandia and the Department of Defense (DOD) Photovoltaic Review Committee. An ultracapacitor, a recent hi-tech development that is environmentally clean, will be incorporated in the PVCPSYS when required to enhance the system's capability. A photovoltaic/ultracapacitor (or equivalent) combined power source operating under adverse conditions, and/or to satisfy or meet regulations will assure cathodic protection, including pipelines carrying combustibles or other products that could otherwise create environmental problems. Patents are pending on this PVCPSYS and the photovoltaic/ultracapacitor powered systems.

The objective of the initial project was to successfully demonstrate that renewable energy can efficiently and economically replace, or be used instead of, continuous non-renewable power sources. An opportunity to clearly show that photovoltaic power is practical and reliable was the result of a recommendation to provide cathodic protection to the Naval Diving and Salvage Training Center bulkhead.

The COASTSYSTA in Panama City, Florida, has broken new ground in the application of solar energy for cathodic protection. Photovoltaic arrays without

battery backup have been connected to the 775-foot steel sheet piling of a dock bulkhead via a cathodic protection system to prevent corrosion on that steel structure in a salt water environment.

As the name signifies, cathodic protection is the process by which, in the COASTSYSTA impressed current type application, the entire steel sheet piling is transformed into a cathode via a series of anodes mounted in PVC standoff racks, in the water, next to the piling. When direct current (DC) energy is applied to the anodes and sufficient electrical potential is attained by current flow from the anodes via an electrolyte (seawater) to the piling, the corrosion is transferred to the anodes, preventing piling corrosion.

Mr. Wally Muehl, electrical/mechanical engineer at COASTSYSTA, was evaluating power sources to protect the Naval Diving and Salvage Training Center bulkhead when he focused on photovoltaics. Although there were 10 other impressed current cathodic protection systems installed on the docks, all were powered by a continuous power source with the current rectified to DC. Of these 10 systems, 5 were down from 1 to 1-1/2 years and 3 were down for more than 2 years due to rectifier failures and/or the power source secured due to construction. As a result, no corrosion protection was provided. PVCPSYS's would have continued to provide power and corrosion protection and would not have been affected by these type power outages.

The Naval Diving and Salvage Training Center is in a separate location from these docks, and it was determined that power was not readily available and would be expensive to provide rectifiers on the dock due to the dock configuration. Rectifiers would also pose a safety hazard on the

dock that is regularly used for diver and salvage training. This bulkhead was 12-years old and other than the initial coating, received no corrosion protection.

Mr. Muehl developed a state-of-the-art solar powered impressed current cathodic protection system requiring no battery backup power for submerged steel and iron type structures. Innovations in design and method of operation permits the photovoltaic arrays to easily provide and maintain complete continuous corrosion protection without the necessity of DC power backup such as batteries. Battery backup power is considered costly and an environmental problem. To date, all impressed current systems require a continuous DC power supply in order to provide cathodic protection.

The COASTSYSTA photovoltaic power system is a fixed-axis system which is suitable for the Panama City latitude of 30°10'N, 85°22'W. The tilt of the adjustable arrays was set at latitude instead of +15° in January 1990, and has not been changed. This is a good indication that other areas with good distribution, but lower insolation levels, would be excellent prospects for a similar type of photovoltaic powered system. For higher latitudes, there are several other options to improve system performance without battery backup. These include one-axis east/west tracking, two-axis north/south, east/west tracking, or simply adding a module or two to meet the additional current requirements. Note: In the Northern Hemisphere, true south should be used in the design, not magnetic south. In most areas, this varies from the magnetic south given by a compass. Magnetic variation could be substantial and can be determined from a isogonic map. This is given in degrees east or west of magnetic south.

Two other problems had to be considered and resolved in order to install an impressed current cathodic protection system. The first problem was ensuring that the steel piling had electrical continuity. Another problem was providing sufficient impression of current "carry over" to overcome a 155-foot section of piling that had to be bypassed, and provide cathodic protection, without anode placement in the area having a water depth of 27 feet where diving takes place. Both problems

were overcome in the design.

To facilitate the use of a photovoltaic powered cathodic protection system without battery backup, the steel sheet pilings were provided an initial one-time only preconditioning polarization for a predetermined continuous time period to the extent that these pilings were initially polarized to a relatively high negative potential by a temporary DC power source. The photovoltaic power system was provided with blocking diodes to prevent any possibility of current reversal. It is to be noted that possible evolution of a protective hydrogen film is merely a by-product of the preconditioning polarization at the higher negative potentials. Additionally, depending upon the environment and if higher (more negative) polarized potentials could be maintained other than required to provide basic complete cathodic protection, formation of thicker calcareous deposits having protective value over a period of time could occur. The initial DC power for polarization can be provided by a DC power source such as a portable, motor-driven DC welder or generator.

The COASTSYSTA PVCPSYS tests performed, along with other data obtained, provide a further explanation that the anode/seawater/cathode piling structure acts like a battery, and when allowed to rest the polarity level recovers and is electrochemical in nature. An electrochemical lead/acid battery, for example, can recover charge if allowed to rest after serving a load. The electrochemical reaction reverses slightly when the load is disconnected; however, a capacitor without an external current source cannot recover by simply removing the load. It is believed that the one-time only initial preconditioning polarization (controlled conditions) of the structure embeds single hydrogen atoms in the steel sheet piling that can also migrate and diffuse in the structure. This system delays the decay of the negative potential and permits the photovoltaic arrays to supply sufficient power; thus allowing the system to easily provide complete, continuous cathodic corrosion protection in situations which include cloudy, overcast, rainy and nighttime conditions without the necessity for DC power backup such as batteries. Re: The Hydrogen Program Manager for the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) has reviewed our PVCPSYS data, and also believes that

pre-polarization (controlled conditions) in a similar environment can embed single hydrogen atoms in the mild steel piling that can also migrate and diffuse in the structure.

The foregoing novel method and system of a one-time only preconditioning or prepolarization of the structure prior to energizing the photovoltaic solar array on-line with the system, provides a relatively higher negative potential that has a slow rate of decay. This permits the use of regulated photovoltaic solar energy with excess available power, and without any backup power, to easily provide complete continuous corrosion protection with excellent polarization levels and improving with time. An analogy may be that the steel structure becomes very effectively polarized and remains so by the variable DC charge affect provided by the simple solar array system, much like a piece of steel or iron can become magnetized by the application of a DC electrical current.

The installation, start up, and continuing operation, including underwater inspections, are well documented to date by COASTSYSTA and verified on site, during the day and at night by the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Construction Engineering Research Laboratory, Naval Energy Program Office, and members of the DOD Photovoltaic Review Committee. According to the National Weather Service, the average amount of available sunshine for the three weeks prior to visits by these organizations averaged 24 percent.

In 1985, the estimated cost of a conventional cathodic protection system requiring continuous DC power was \$75,000.00. In 1990, the estimated cost was \$108,000.00. The PVCPSYS cost at contract completion was \$61,316.00, complete and ready to use. The initial cost savings by installing a PVCPSYS was in excess of \$46,000.00. The DOD Photovoltaic Review Committee and Sandia National Laboratories consider this successful and cost effective system a major advance for the application of photovoltaics.

This system has been in operation over five years and has not required maintenance or adjustment. A patent is pending on the new technology. Other possible applications include mothballed ships, docks, dams, locks,

bridges, marinas, offshore structures, and pipelines in various environments.

A photovoltaic power system without any backup power was installed on another 800-foot bulkhead. The two previous 400-foot conventional rectifier powered impressed current cathodic protection systems were modified to allow this conversion. The PVCPSYS successfully started operation on 21 May 1993, without any backup power and is providing complete continuous corrosion protection. A state-of-the-art data collection system is provided via a personal computer that is MS-DOS compatible and located about 1/2 mile away from the site. Along with other capabilities this system will simultaneously monitor, report, analyze, and record the solar energy output in DC volts, DC amps, as well as the DC negative potential of the steel sheet piling.

When required a recent high-tech development ultracapacitor or equivalent that is also environmentally clean will be incorporated into the PVCPSYS to enhance the system's capability. A photovoltaic/ultracapacitor combined power source will assure cathodic protection for submerged or buried steel or iron type structures. It is also effective under adverse conditions and will satisfy environmental regulations in such applications as pipelines carrying combustible materials. Westinghouse Electric Corporation acquired the rights to manufacture the ultracapacitor and has expressed an interest in the combined PVCPU/ultracapacitor system.

The ultracapacitor technology developed over the past 12 years by Pinnacle Research Institute, Inc. (PRI), provides both high energy and power. The capacitor breaks all paradigms associated with conventional batteries and capacitors. The ultracapacitor has no conventional dielectric. Unlike batteries there is no chemical reaction; therefore, the ultracapacitor can be discharged and rapidly recharged by photovoltaic power for an indefinite number of times. (Testing by U. S. DoE confirms over 120,000 cycles of operation). Further, it's sponge-like surface gives the plate an actual surface area that is 100,000 times greater than the same surface of the same plate if it were smooth. The higher surface area allows more energy

to be stored. The ultracapacitor has 100 times more power per ounce and is significantly smaller than conventional capacitors. Most importantly, a second generation of ultracapacitors has been recently developed that are capable of releasing energy gradually. An ultracapacitor (if required for the COASTSYSTA PVCPSYS installed in 1993) would weigh about 18 pounds. In the electric powered automobile industry, for example, some initial applications will be for hill climbing and acceleration. PRI is a subcontractor of the Department of Energy Hybrid Electric Vehicle Program.

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